

SPATIAL

SPATIAL at the IoT Week 2022!

SPATIAL will participate in the IoT Week 2022 on "Trust and privacy in an intelligent, smart IoT World. Challenges and outcomes" - Session 2: #AI and #ML technologies as enablers for a more secure #IoT represented by its partner AUSTRALO.

[Check the speakers](#)

Learn more about the SPATIAL partners on those interviews! Discover how they enrolled on the project, their expectations and how they see the upcoming future for SPATIAL.

[PARTNERS](#)

SPATIAL participated in the EuCnC 6G Summit by its partner University College of Dublin, UCD, which presented two accepted papers. The dissemination partner, AUSTRALO, also attended the event.

[READ about the presented papers](#)

Our collaborators

We work with a range of parallel projects in common areas of research to maximise our impact and network reach. Check the events where our collaborators will participate in June.

[Check the events](#)

SPATIAL - info@spatial-h2020.eu

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